

RELIABILITY OF TWO IR MOTION CAPTURE SYSTEMS IN A MUSIC PERFORMANCE SETTING

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes a comparative analysis of tracking quality in two infrared marker-based motion capture systems: one older but high-end (Qualisys, purchased in 2009) and the other newer and mid-range (OptiTrack, purchased in 2019). We recorded performances by a string quartet with both systems simultaneously, using the same frame rate. Our recording set-up included a combination of moving markers (affixed to musicians' bodies) and stationary markers (affixed to music stands). Higher noise levels were observed in Qualisys recordings of stationary markers than in OptiTrack recordings, as well as a greater spatial range, though OptiTrack recordings had a higher rate of outliers ("spikes" in the signal). In moving markers, increased quantity of motion was associated with increased between-system error rates. Both systems showed minimal within-trial drift but a reduction in recording accuracy and precision over the duration of the experiment. Overall, our results show that the older/high-end system (Qualisys) produced slightly lower-quality recordings than the newer/mid-range system (OptiTrack). We discuss how our findings may inform researchers' interpretations of motion capture data, particularly when capturing the types of motion that are important for performing music.

1. INTRODUCTION

Music-related motion is commonly examined through the use of optical motion capture (MoCap). Infrared (IR) passive marker-based systems are particularly useful as they allow for relatively free movement and detailed but versatile data collection. In recent years, IR MoCap systems have been used to study a range of performance movement types, including the fine-grained finger movements of pianists [1], the coarticulation of drum strokes [2], the bowing of violinists [3], the ancillary movements of clarinetists [4], and the alignment of instrumentalists' head movements with sound onsets [5].

Certain technical challenges arise in the study of music-related motion. For example, to capture music performances in ecologically valid conditions, portable MoCap systems (including smaller IR systems) might be preferred, though

Figure 1: From a rehearsal with the string quartet in the recording space. The cameras of the two MoCap systems (Qualisys and Optitrack) can be seen near the ceiling.

such systems may sacrifice some recording precision. Similarly, long recordings can be affected by drift, but may be needed to capture performances in full (e.g., in studies of concert behaviour). Drift is less of an issue for IR systems than for inertial systems, but may still arise.

Occlusion—that is, the visual blocking of markers from the cameras—can be a particular issue when working with passive marker-based systems. This may be due to the types of movement involved in instrumental performance, as well as the presence of instruments, music stands, and sometimes multiple performers. Such occlusions can be overcome by strategic marker positioning. A question that arises with fine movements (e.g., pianists' finger movements) is how to avoid misidentification between rapidly moving, closely positioned markers. Recent research suggests that a sampling rate should be chosen that is proportional to the ratio between maximum marker speed and minimum marker spacing [6].

Since researchers work with different types of MoCap systems—which may vary in features such as cost, portability, or intrusiveness—it is necessary to understand how their data compare to be able to make informed judgments of the reported results. Previous studies compared a high-end IR MoCap system (Qualisys) with an iPod Touch [7] and an inertial armband sensor (AX3, Axivity) [8]. While the high-end system unsurprisingly records with greater precision, the wearable sensors provide sufficiently useful data and might be preferred for some real-world settings.

Another comparative study tested noise levels in recordings from a high-end system (Qualisys) and a more affordable system (OptiTrack) [9]. The high-end system recorded a stationary marker with 5–6 times less noise than did the

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more affordable system. Both systems showed some drift over the course of a 30 minute recording, but the magnitude was very slight compared to the more substantial drift that is shown by some inertial sensors [10, 11].

The current study tested the quality of marker tracking in a naturalistic music performance setting. We compared the performance of a high-end system (Qualisys; hereafter HE), using the same cameras as tested in [9], which are now around 10 years old, with the performance of a mid-range system (OptiTrack; hereafter MR), which was around 1 year old at the time of testing. The latter system is primarily intended as a less costly, portable alternative for testing out of the lab. Both systems were set up in the fourMs lab at the University of Oslo and used to record performances of a string quartet.

2. EXPERIMENT SETUP AND METHOD

2.1 Equipment

Motion data were collected using two optical motion capture systems that recorded simultaneously: a Qualisys system with 12 Oqus 300 cameras, and an OptiTrack system with 8 Flex 13 cameras. The Qualisys system is a fixed installation in the lab space. Cameras are positioned around the full lab volume, attached to a metal frame near ceiling level. The OptiTrack system was temporarily set up for the purpose of these recordings. Its cameras were positioned around the half of the lab in which the string quartet played and were fixed to the same metal frame as the Qualisys cameras (Figure 1).

Each member of the string quartet wore a jacket with 6 reflective markers attached (head, upper back, left and right upper and lower arms). Markers were also placed in the corner of each musician’s music stand. The musicians wore eye tracking glasses while they played, and each set of glasses had 4 markers attached in a unique configuration (Figure 2).

Both systems recorded with a sampling rate of 120 Hz. A visual signal was captured using a clapperboard at the start of each recording, and timestamps were synchronized retrospectively. Data for individual performances were extracted from the recordings. These were trimmed to include only data from 5 seconds before piece onset until 5 seconds after the final note onset. Motion capture data were labelled and exported in TSV (Qualisys, QTM) or CSV (OptiTrack, Motive) file formats. No further postprocessing of the data was done. All analyses were done in R [12].

2.2 Recording procedure

The string quartet performed Haydn’s String Quartet Op. 76, No. 4 in B-flat major, I. Allegro con spirito and II. Adagio. An excerpt of the first movement (Allegro) was recorded 5 times, and the full movement was recorded once. The entire second movement (Adagio) was also recorded once. The five performances of the Allegro excerpt were done as part of an experiment investigating visual coordination. The musicians were alone in the lab for these performances, and played in different spatial configurations

Figure 2: Close-up of two musicians from the string quartet, with MoCap suits and eye tracking glasses. Markers were placed on each note stand.

(e.g., back-to-back, facing each other in a semi-circle, or with the 1st violinist behind a curtain). The final performance of the complete Allegro and the performance of the Adagio were given under concert conditions; an audience of approximately 40 people filled the remaining space in the lab. The full recording session lasted approximately 3 hours (including some breaks).

2.3 Analysis of motion features

Only markers that were tracked successfully (i.e., that could be labelled) through at least 85% of both HE and MR recordings were included in the analysis. The markers that could be analysed for each trial are listed in Table 1.

To allow for some statistical comparisons, we divided each of the (7) performances into 20 windows of approximately equal length. Since performances differed in duration, windows did not span the same length of time for all trials. Several of our dependent variables were calculated per window, as described below.

2.3.1 Quantity of Motion

Quantity of motion (QoM) was calculated per window and per dimension (x, y, z, and 3D) for each motion trajectory using unmodified position values. We calculated the first derivative of position values (velocity) for each MoCap system. QoM was then calculated as the sum of absolute velocities divided by the total duration of the window. For a vector comprising MR position values o_1, o_2, \dots, o_n , and HE position values q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n ,

$$QoM = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{i=2}^n \left| \frac{(o_i - o_{(i-1)}) + (q_i - q_{(i-1)})}{2} \right| \quad (1)$$

where n is the total number of samples and T is the total duration of the window. QoM was considered as a predictor variable for moving markers and comprised the primary dependent variable for stationary markers, serving as an indicator of noise level in (what should nominally be) a static signal.

2.3.2 Between-System Errors in Marker Position

For each marker trajectory (3D and in x, y, and z dimensions individually), the initial position was subtracted from

each subsequent position. This created “distance from start” vectors of values for each marker. These vectors would, in theory, be identical for the two MoCap systems if they recorded without noise or error.

Mean squared errors (MSEs) were calculated between pairs of vectors (HE vs. MR), per window, as a measure of the difference between them. For moving markers, these MSEs comprised the primary dependent variable.

2.3.3 Spatial Range

We calculated the spatial range that was captured by each system in each dimension. Spatial range was obtained per window for all marker trajectories and was calculated in two ways: 1) as the difference between the maximum and minimum position values that were recorded by the two systems, and 2) as the standard deviation of the distribution of marker positions. The first measure provides an “absolute” range and the second provides a “representative” range that is less affected by outliers (“spikes”, see below).

2.3.4 Drift and Spikes

Stationary marker recordings were evaluated for the occurrence of drift and “spikes” in the signal (instantaneous outliers in the series of marker positions; see Figure 3). To check for drift, we used linear regression to calculate the slope of stationary marker trajectories per trial. To identify spikes, we calculated a z-score for each marker position relative to the trial mean and SD. A threshold of $z = \pm 5$ was set, and points beyond this range were considered to be spikes.

2.3.5 Evaluation of Recording Reliability

Distributions of MSEs, QoM values, and spike frequency were positively skewed. Therefore, statistical analysis of these variables was made using generalized linear modelling (GLM) with a gamma distribution. Spatial range values approximated a normal distribution, so GLM with a Gaussian distribution was used.

For stationary markers, we tested for differences in QoM between systems across spatial dimensions, trials, and over time within trials. We checked for evidence of drift as well. For moving markers, we tested how MSEs differed according to QoM, spatial dimension, trial number, and recording duration. We also checked for differences in the spatial range captured by the two systems for both stationary and moving markers.

3. RESULTS

MSEs (mm^2) indicating the magnitude of difference between HE and MR recordings of markers at different locations (arm, back, glasses, head, and music stands) are listed in Table 2, along with mean QoM values. Example data profiles with high and low between-system errors are shown in Figure 3 (stationary markers) and Figure 4 (moving markers).

Errors between recordings were small overall, but substantially larger for moving markers than for stationary mark-

ers. Results for stationary and moving markers are presented separately in the sections below.

Figure 3: Time series showing “difference from start” vectors for MR (OptiTrack, blue) and HE (Qualisys, red) recordings. The upper and lower plots show trials with lower and higher between-system error, respectively.

Figure 4: Time series showing “difference from start” vectors for MR (blue) and HE (red) recordings. The upper and lower plots show trials with low and high between-system errors, respectively.

3.1 Stationary Markers

As can be seen in Figure 3, some noise was present in the recordings of stationary markers. For the most part, noise levels were low: the median QoM for MR and HE recordings were 1.21 mm and 1.96 mm, respectively. However, we did also note occasional spikes in the stationary marker trajectories, as well as some “jumps” where the measured marker position moved suddenly by a fraction of a millimeter before eventually returning to its original position,

Musician	Head	Back	UL Arm	LL Arm	UR Arm	LR Arm	Glasses	Stand
Violinist 1	all	1, 4, 6, 7	1, 3, 6, 7	1-3, 5-7	1-3, 5-7	all	1-3, 5-7*	2-3, 5-7
Violinist 2	all	1	—	—	1	1	1*	2-3, 5-7*
Violist	all	1	1	2-5	1	1	3-7*	3-5
Cellist	all	all	all	all	all	all	all	all

Table 1: Trials with successful marker recordings. “UL” denotes upper left, “LR” denotes lower right, and so on. Note that each music stand and set of glasses included 4 markers, while body locations had one marker per person. (*) indicates trials in which all 4 markers for the glasses or stand were available; in some additional trials, some but not all markers were available.

Marker location	MSE	QoM
Arm	0.67	18.38
Back	0.04	7.85
Glasses	1.26	22.27
Head	0.23	16.39
Stand	1.21	4.06

Table 2: MSEs and QoM for different marker locations. Data have been averaged across musicians and trials.

or a new “stationary position”. Some instances of such jumps and spikes can be seen in Figure 3.

QoM calculations revealed an outlier in the HE data for Trial 1. One marker recorded with very high noise, probably due to its placement near the edge of the capture volume (musicians played back-to-back during this trial). We decided to omit this marker from further analysis. One additional marker was omitted from Trial 4 (window 6 only) due to high noise.

3.1.1 System Differences in Quantity of Motion

QoM of the stationary markers (i.e., the noise level of the system) did not differ between x, y, and z dimensions for either system, so only results for 3D data are presented here. Higher QoM (i.e., greater noise) was seen for HE recordings ($M = 4.52$, $SD = 2.56$) than for MR recordings ($M = 2.23$, $SD = 1.55$), $t(278) = 8.09$, $p < .001$. As we can see from Figure 6, this difference between systems occurred in every trial.

With spatial range quantified as the difference between maximum and minimum position values, the range for HE recordings was larger than the range for MR, $t(260) = 7.04$, $p < .001$ (HE $M = .87$, $SD = .62$; MR $M = .40$, $SD = .35$). Likewise, with spatial range quantified as the SDs of the distributions of marker positions, the range for HE was larger again, $t(278) = 5.56$, $p < .001$ (Figure 6). Spatial range tended to increase across trials for both systems, suggesting a decrease in precision across the recording session.

Both examples in Figure 3 show some spikes in the marker trajectory. MR recordings contained a higher frequency of spikes (i.e., a higher number of spikes relative to the total number of samples) than HE recordings, $t(276) = 3.00$, $p = .003$; this effect was consistent across almost all trials (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Frequency of spikes across trials for MR and HE recordings.

Figure 6: QoM (left) and spatial range (right) for stationary markers across conditions in MR and HE recordings.

3.1.2 Trial number and recording time

Drift was visible in some individual marker trajectories. However, neither average signed slope magnitudes nor average absolute slope magnitudes differed systematically between the two MoCap systems. Looking across the recording session, we observed an effect of trial number on QoM, $t(278) = 9.14$, $p < .001$. As shown in Figure 6, noise level generally increased across trials for both systems, suggesting a decrease in recording precision over time.

3.2 Moving Markers

3.2.1 Spatial Dimension and Range

Figure 8 shows how MSEs (calculated per window, trial, and marker location) differed between spatial dimensions.

Figure 7: QoM per window across each of Trials 1–7. Blue and red lines are MR and HE recordings, respectively. Colours follow a gradient from dark (Trial 1) to light (Trial 7).

Movement along the y (vertical) axis yielded lower errors than movement along the x axis, $t(237) = 9.92, p < .001$, or z axis, $t(237) = 10.22, p < .001$. QoM was also lower in the y direction ($M = 39.3, SD = 26.5$) than in the x direction ($M = 51.6, SD = 25.1$) or z direction ($M = 50.82, SD = 24.31$).

Figure 8: MSEs for x, y, and z dimensions for different marker locations (left) and between-system differences in spatial range. Negative differences indicate a larger spatial range in HE recordings. Error bars indicate standard error.

Between-system differences in spatial range (quantified in terms of maximum-minimum unidimensional position differences) were calculated (Figure 8). Negative differences indicate that HE recordings had a larger spatial range; positive differences indicate that the range was larger for MR. Differences were more negative in the x direction than in the y direction, $t(237) = 5.17, p < .001$, but did not differ statistically for the y and z directions. The same pattern of results was found when spatial range was quantified in terms of the SD of the distributions of unidimensional marker positions.

3.2.2 Quantity of Motion

We tested for an effect of quantity of motion (QoM) on error magnitude for 3D variables. Two outliers were removed before running the analysis (both with a z-score

> 9). A plot showing the relationship between MSEs and QoM (calculated per window, trial, and marker location) is given in Figure 9. GLM indicated a positive effect of QoM on MSEs, $t(556) = 21.27, p < .001$. Thus, it seems that errors increased for markers that moved more during the course of a recording.

Figure 9: Scatterplot showing a positive relationship between MSEs and QoM for 3D variables.

3.2.3 Trial number and recording duration

MSEs per trial and marker location are shown in Figure 10. A marginally significant effect of trial number emerged, $t(558) = 1.98, p = .048$; however, this effect is not easily explained. MSEs did not systematically increase across trials, which would have indicated a decrease in recording quality across the experiment. Differences were not systematic according to playing conditions (e.g., conditions were the same for Trials 3 and 5, and the spatial configuration of musicians was the same for Trials 2, 3, and 5–7). QoM might account for some variability in errors. A GLM that included QoM as a covariate yielded a better fit (AIC -121.82) than a GLM that included only trial number as a predictor (AIC 85.84).

Changes in MSEs over time within recordings are shown in Figure 11. MSEs generally (slightly) increased across the course of recordings, but GLM did not indicate a significant effect. Thus, any decline in quality that occurred during the course of individual recordings was minimal.

Figure 10: MSEs (left) and QoM (right) for Trials 1–7.

Figure 11: MSE per window across each of Trials 1–7. The black line indicates the slope given by a linear regression of window number on MSEs.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the noise levels and tracking reliability of an older high-end motion capture system and a newer mid-range system. Our results can be summarized as follows. For stationary markers:

- The HE system recorded with higher noise levels than the MR system. The HE system gave higher QoM as well as larger absolute (max–min) and representative (SD) spatial ranges.
- In contrast, the MR system showed a greater frequency of spikes and sudden jumps in the signal.
- We saw minimal evidence of drift within individual recordings for both systems. However, recording quality declined somewhat across the course of the 3-hour session.

For moving markers:

- Tracking reliability was greater in both horizontal dimensions (x and z) than in the vertical dimension (y).
- A more negative spatial range was captured for the x dimension than for the y dimension, indicating a larger range in HE than MR recordings. In the z dimension, the HE system captured a larger range for all but arm markers, where a larger range was captured by the MR system.
- QoM was strongly related to the magnitude of between-system errors.
- Drift did not have a measurable effect on tracking reliability, and we saw no systematic decline in quality over the course of the session.

These results should be considered in light of the findings by Jensenius et al. [9], which compared the same HE system to an earlier version of the MR system, and found better performance by the HE system. The noise levels we

found for the HE system are on par with those recorded in [9]. The improved performance that we found for the MR system in the current study speaks to the progress that has been made in motion capture technologies. It is clear that MR motion capture systems today perform at a very high level.

We would recommend that researchers consider the noise behaviour of the MoCap systems that they work with, and take this into consideration when smoothing and filtering their data. For example, our MR system produced noise within a smaller range of values than the HE system, but was more likely to make spikes and jumps. It can be useful to record (and report) some stationary markers alongside the target markerset—ideally, positioned as close as possible to the space that the target markers will use—in order to monitor the noise level of the MoCap system in use.

To maximize the quality of MoCap recordings, we would also recommend that researchers make multiple calibrations if testing across a period of hours. We saw a slight increase in noise levels across trials. While this did not seem to affect tracking quality for moving markers, it is important to keep in mind, especially if studying fine or small-scale movements that might be more distorted by jitter.

We had to exclude a number of markers from analysis due to high occlusion rates, which is difficult to avoid when capturing multiple musicians in a relatively tight space. A couple of additional “well-tracked” markers had to be excluded, because their placement close to the edge of the capture volume meant that their trajectories contained very high levels of noise. This shows the importance of situating your target markers well within the bounds of the capture volume, as well as thoroughly calibrating the full volume [9].

Finally, our study showed a strong relationship between QoM and between-system errors. We would therefore advise some caution in making detailed analysis of trajectories that contain high QoM. In line with the 2016 paper by Song and Godøy [6], it is important to select a sufficiently high frame rate if there is fast motion in markers that are spatially close together. In our case, the markers that were attached to the eye-tracking glasses were relatively close together, which did cause some issues with misidentification. In the specific setup that we tested, markers with a high QoM might also have been difficult to track for some other reasons (e.g., arm markers were subject to relatively frequent occlusion).

In sum, these findings show the high reliability with which IR motion capture systems can track human movements in a music performance setting, and highlight the need for careful marker placement, monitoring of noise levels, and informed selection of effective filtering methods.

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5. REFERENCES

- [1] W. Goebel and C. Palmer, “Tactile feedback and timing accuracy in piano performance,” *Experimental Brain Research*, vol. 186, pp. 471–479, 2008.
- [2] R. I. Godøy, M. Song, and S. Dahl, “Exploring Sound Motion Textures In Drum Set Performance,” in *Proceedings of the Sound and Music Computing Conference*, 2017.
- [3] N. Rasamimanana and F. Bevilacqua, “Effort-based analysis of bowing movements: Evidence of anticipation effects,” *Journal of New Music Research*, vol. 37, no. 4, pp. 339–351, 2008.
- [4] M. Nusseck and M. M. Wanderley, “Music and Motion—How Music-Related Ancillary Body Movements Contribute to the Experience of Music,” *Music perception: An interdisciplinary journal*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 335–353, 2009.
- [5] L. Bishop and W. Goebel, “Communication for coordination: Gesture kinematics and conventionality affect synchronization success in piano duos,” *Psychological Research*, vol. 82, pp. 1177–1194, 2018.
- [6] M. Song and R. I. Godøy, “How fast is your body motion? determining a sufficient frame rate for an optical motion tracking system using passive markers,” *PLoS One*, vol. 11, p. e010993, 2016.
- [7] K. Nymoen, A. Voldsund, S. A. Skogstad, A. R. Jensenius, and J. Torresen, “Comparing motion data from an ipod touch to an optical infrared marker-based motion capture system,” in *Proc. Int. Conf. New Interfaces for Musical Expression*, Ann Arbor, 2012.
- [8] R. T. Solberg and A. R. Jensenius, “Optical or inertial? evaluation of two motion capture systems for studies of dancing to electronic dance music,” in *Proc. Int. Conf. Sound and Music Computing*, Hamburg, 2016.
- [9] A. R. Jensenius, K. Nymoen, S. A. Skogstad, and A. Voldsund, “A study of the noise-level in two infrared marker-based motion capture systems,” in *Proc. Int. Conf. Sound and Music Computing*, Copenhagen, 2012.
- [10] S. A. Skogstad, K. Nymoen, Y. de Quay, and A. R. Jensenius, “Osc implementation and evaluation of the Xsens MVN suit,” in *Proc. Int. Conf. New Interfaces for Musical Expression*, Oslo, 2011.
- [11] G. Vigiensoni and M. M. Wanderley, “A Quantitative Comparison of Position Trackers for the Development of a Touch-less Musical Interface,” in *Proceedings of the International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression*, Ann Arbor, MI, 2012.
- [12] R Core Team, *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*, R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.R-project.org/>